

ISic3590

Honours for an emperor

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

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Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2011.06.15

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

From the excavations of the agora

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory 30605

Physical Description

13 joining fragments of a slab of off-white marble (no veining). Height 62.5 cm; width 47.5 cm; depth 2cm (top left), 2.3cm (top right), c.3 cm (base). Intact left, right and at base, but the upper portion is missing, as is one fragment from within the body of the surviving section. Traces of a line of mortar following a line parallel to the edge of the stone are preserved on the face, suggesting that it was at some point subsequently fixed face inwards to another surface, implying subsequent re-use.

Dimensions

Height 62.5 cm

Width 47.5 cm

Depth 2-3 cm

Layout

Remains of three lines of Latin text are preserved, together with guide-lines top and bottom of each line. A further three guide lines are preserved below the last line of the text, but with no traces of letters.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters decrease from 60mm in line 1, to 42-43 mm in line 2 and 35 mm in line 3. The letters are fairly crudely V-cut, not always maintaining the vertical. V is very broad and irregular; E tall and narrow; R has a very small, closed eye; P a large elongated eye; G is tall and narrow. Serifs are basic, as are the triangular interpuncts which occur at every word division.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 60 mm

Line 2: 42-43 mm

Line 3: 35 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: not measured mm

Text

undefined. [---]

1. Aug(usto) ·

2. Res · P(ublica) · Hal(aesinorum) ·

3. (vac.unknown)D(ecreto) · D(ecurionum) · (vac.unknown)

undefined. (vac.undefined)

Apparatus

Text from autopsy and study for edition of 2017

Translation (en)

To [--?--] Augustus; the res publica of the people of Halaesa, by decree of the town councillors.

Commentary

It is reasonable to assume that the full titulature of one of the third-century emperors is lost from the first part of the stone, as exemplified by ISic3586 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3586>] , ISic3587 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3587>] , ISic3588 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3588>] . The use of the formula res publica Halaesinorum is also found in ISic3587 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3587>] (for Traianus Decius), and the presence of D.D. in this text might encourage its restoration at the end of that text. This is not the lower part of ISic3588 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3588>] (to Volusianus) since both the stone and the lettering are different.

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Bibliography

Prag, J.R.W., Tigano, G. 2017. Alesa Archonidea : il lapidarium. *Introduzione all'archeologia di Halaesa*. Palermo. At no.31

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